

Optimization of 3D Woven Composites for Bearing Performance in Double Lap Joints Using Acoustic Emissions.

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Agenda

Introduction & Motivation

**Research Objective &
Methodology**

**3D Woven Architectures &
Test Setup**

Bearing Performance Results

Acoustic Emission Analysis

Conclusions & Future Work

Project Overview

Novel 3D+ multi-axial preforms for complex loaded composite applications

Project Reference:
EP/X036804/1

Project Scope

Artemis
TECHNOLOGIES

SPIRIT
AEROSYSTEMS®

- Development and performance optimisation of a novel 3D+ hybrid composite material for structurally demanding joint applications such as lugs
- Integration of a 3D woven core with off-axis 2D fibre overlays to enable:
 - Through-thickness reinforcement
 - Multi-directional load accommodation
- Emphasis on transition of weave architectures within the preform to tailor local performance
 - From global structural stiffness
 - To enhance damage tolerance at stress-critical regions such as bolt holes
- Ultimate aim: facilitate wider adoption of composite joints in load-critical structures

Significance

Supports Net-Zero Targets

Enhancing joint performance enables broader structural integration of composites in transport systems aligned with Net-Zero goals.

Tailors Material to Application

By integrating architecture transitions and off-axis fibres, the material can be optimised for specific loading conditions within a component.

Addresses Through-Thickness

The 3D+ hybrid architecture provides through-thickness reinforcement, increase delamination resistance and crack propagation

Industry-Ready and Scalable

Using existing manufacturing methods, the proposed material system is scalable without major capital investment.

Research Hypothesis

3D Core

- Primary failure in composite lugs from fibre buckling & breakage near hole region – progressing to inter-laminar fracture.
- Will provide bulk reinforcement to improve inter-laminar strength, increase strain to failure, bearing response and damage resistance.
- Orthogonal weave architecture – shown to have the highest bearing response.

2D Layers

- Off-axis NCF
- Increase shear properties for out-of-plane loading

Objectives and Goals

Objectives and Goals

Objective 1 ✓

Analyse complex loading scenarios using two industrial case studies (Spirit Aero and ATL) to define design requirements and loading conditions for novel preforms.

Objective 4

Investigate interlaminar behaviour between 3D and 2D layers to assess fibre interaction and local through-thickness performance.

Objective 2

Manufacture and characterise innovative 3D architectures to understand their mechanical behaviour under bearing load cases.

Objective 5

Develop a comprehensive material database for 3D and 3D+ architectures to support initial design rule generation.

Objective 3

Design and produce hybrid 3D+ preforms with off-axis 2D fibre overlays to evaluate mechanical response in bearing conditions.

Introduction

Objective 2

Double-Lap Joint & Bearing Performance

Double-lap pinned joints, evaluate the bearing response of composite materials under compressive contact loads introduced by a fastener.

- Symmetric geometry eliminates secondary bending,
- Provides a more controlled and repeatable stress distribution at the hole
- Preferred for isolating the material response without geometry-induced artefacts

This study employs double-lap testing to isolate the mechanical response of the material, enabling a clear evaluation of how the 3D woven architecture affects bearing performance.

- Minimises joint-induced complexities and enables direct comparison of factors like binder content and fibre paths, while focusing on through-thickness performance and preventing early global failure.

Composite Manufacture

Parameter	Value / Description
Warp yarn count	500 ends
Yarn type	T700 12k 50c carbon tows, 800 tex
Reed size	8 per inch
Reed width	600 cm
Denting pattern	1-4-1-4
Dent repeat length	4 dents
Reed type	Stainless, open-slot
Loom type	Weaverbird Dobby Loom
Tensioning method	Spring Tensioned Bobbins

- **RTM test panel tooling**

- Adjustable cavity up to 50mm thick
- Solid glass top plate for flow observation
- Electrical heating for in-mould cure up to 180°C
- 4 x sensor ports – combination of dielectric cure monitoring, resin arrival (in tool flow monitoring), pressure, temperature.

Test Setup & Bearing Visualisation

- Double-lap joint tested under tensile loading
- Test follows ASTM D5961 – Procedure A
- 6 mm bolt with light torque to simulate preload
- Load applied at 2 mm/min to induce bearing failure
- COD Gauge used to track hole deformation
- Designed to replicate realistic joint behavior in lugs

Parameter	Details
Specimen Width	36 mm
Specimen Length	135 mm
Hole Diameter	6 mm
Edge Distance	18 mm
Fibre Orientations	0/45/90
Fastener	6mm Steel 12.9
Torque Value	2 Nm
Gauge Length	10mm

Industrial Applications of Acoustic Emission (AE) Monitoring

- Aerospace structures: AE monitors aircraft components like wings and fuselage for damage, ensuring structural integrity.
- Wind turbine blades: AE detects internal damage during fatigue and assesses manufacturing quality in thick-section composites.
- Pressure vessels and pipelines: AE validates the integrity of composite-wrapped tanks under composite monocoques, particularly in motorsport and EVs.
- Civil infrastructure: AE covers bridge panels, prestressed FRP rebars, and retrofitted concrete to monitor damage progression.
- Marine structures: AE inspects hulls and bulkheads in FRP ships and offshore platforms under wave loading.

Acoustic Emission (AE) Monitoring

- AE detects high-frequency stress waves from internal damage events (matrix cracking, delamination, fibre breakage).
- In double-lap bearing tests, the fixture obstructs visual access to the damage zone — AE provides real-time, internal damage detection.
- AE allows identification of first damage initiation, even before measurable load drops occur.
- Enables comparison of performance across fibre orientations and architectures.

AE Sensor Configuration and System Validation

Parameter	Details
Sensor Type	NANO -30
Frequency Range	20 kHz – 1 MHz
Sensor Placement	Mounted underneath, left and right of the bolt centerline
Coupling Medium	Hot Glue
Threshold	35 dB
Sampling Rate	5 MSPS

System Calibration:

- Verified sensor coupling and response using **Hsu-Nielsen pencil lead break method** (ASTM E976)
- Signal reproducibility confirmed through multiple breaks at known locations
- Validated propagation path and sensor sensitivity (Before and After)

Sample 1	Date	28/07/2025	Material	3D Orthogonal Double Lap			
	Accept Range	Lower	Upper				
		90	100				
	Channel	Breaks (dB)			Average	In/Out	After Rem.1
	1	98	98	98	98	In	
2	99	98	98	98.33	In		

Term	Value
PDT (Peak Definition Time)	50 μ s
HDT (Hit Definition Time)	100 μ s
HLT (Hit Lockout Time)	300 μ s
Max Duration	100 ms

3D Woven Orthogonal Float 1 and Float 2

3D Orthogonal Float 1

Parameter	Float 1	Float 2	% Change	Units
Warp Yarns per cm	8.33	8.2	-1.56%	yarns/cm
Weft Yarns per cm	16.1	25.3	57.14%	yarns/cm
Compressed Thickness (avg.)	2.5	2.8	12.00%	mm
Areal Weight	0.181	0.259	43.09%	g/cm ²
Fibre Volume Fraction	50.3–51.0	51.3–53.2	+2.59% to +4.31%	%
Weft Yarn Length (per pick)	2.576	3.657	41.96%	mm
Distance Between Weft Yarns	2.565	4.215	64.33%	mm

3D Orthogonal Float 2

Yarn Type	Float 1	Float 2	% Change	Units
Warp	0.27	0.06	77.78%	%
Weft (Top)	0.35	0.49	-40.00%	%
Weft (Bottom)	0.93	2.07	-122.58%	%
Binder	59.12	48.78	17.49%	%

Double Lap Results

Double Lap Results

- Float 2 reduced ultimate strength at all orientations ($\downarrow 15.5\%$ at 0° , $\downarrow 2.0\%$ at 45° , $\downarrow 3.6\%$ at 90°).
- Bearing stiffness improved with Float 2 at 45° ($+11.3\%$), due to straighter fibre paths and reduced crimp, at the cost of a modest reduction in ultimate strength
- Float 1 shows more robust performance at 0° and 90° , attributed to higher interlacement density, enhancing through-thickness load transfer.

Orientation	Float Length	Bearing Stiffness (MPa)	Diff (%)	Ultimate Bearing Strength (MPa)	Diff (%)
0°	Float 1	55.95		810.78	
	Float 2	42.54	-23.97%	684.83	-15.53%
45°	Float 1	33.32		784.02	
	Float 2	37.08	+11.28%	768.12	-2.03%
90°	Float 1	61.09		787.6	
	Float 2	60.08	-1.65%	759.26	-3.60%

Double Lap Failure

- All specimens failed via bearing-dominated mechanisms, with variation across orientations
- Shear-out observed at 90°, confirming dominant inter-yarn shear failure
- Cleavage and lateral splitting are most common at a 45° angle, influenced by off-axis stresses.

3D Woven Orthogonal Double Lap Bearing

3D ORTH	Orientation	Failure
Float 1	0	Bearing/Lateral
	45	Bearing/Cleavage
	90	Bearing/Shear out
Float 2	0	Bearing/Lateral
	45	Bearing/Cleavage
	90	Bearing/Shear out

Acoustic Emission Results – 0° Orientation

- Float 1 exhibits delayed AE onset, indicating later initiation of damage near the hole.
- Float 2 shows early, high-energy AE events, suggesting premature fibre buckling or matrix fracture.
- Cumulative AE energy is higher in Float 1, consistent with more progressive damage accumulation.
- Conclusion: Float 1 provides enhanced bearing damage resistance under loading due to greater through-thickness confinement.

Acoustic Emission Results – 45° Orientation

- Float 2 generates a higher AE event rate and broader energy distribution during loading.
- Indicates distributed micro-damage and improved shear load transfer from reduced tow crimp.
- Cumulative AE energy is spread across the load range, which could imply gradual matrix–fibre interaction.
- Conclusion: Float 2 demonstrates improved shear-bearing response, despite a minor reduction in ultimate bearing strength

Acoustic Emission Results – 90° Orientation

- Weft yarns aligned with load, but failure occurs via shear-out, not net-tension.
- Both Float 1 and 2 show similar AE hit rate and energy profiles.
- AE peaks occur near peak load, indicating sudden damage coalescence typical of a shear out fracture.
- Conclusion: AE confirms that failure at 90° is driven by inter-yarn shear and delamination, not extensive fibre breakage.

Summary

- A novel 3D+ hybrid composite material was developed for structurally demanding joint applications such as lugs.
- The material integrates a 3D woven core with off-axis 2D fibre overlays to enhance through-thickness reinforcement and enable multi-directional load accommodation.
- Weave architecture transitions were introduced within the preform to tailor performance locally around stress-critical regions like bolt holes.
- Double-lap joint testing was used to evaluate the bearing response under controlled tensile loading conditions.
- Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring enabled detection of internal damage mechanisms, including fibre breakage, matrix cracking, and delamination.
- Results showed that different 3D woven architectures affect both damage tolerance and bearing performance depending on fibre orientation.

Thank You

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